

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: RAPPOCCIOLO****FIRST NAME: FRANCESCA****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Punctuation (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 15-23 & 31-32)
2. Plagiarism (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 33-34)
3. Citation (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 34-39)
4. Style Guide and Chicago Style (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 40-44)

ESSAY WRITING AT EUCLID UNIVERSITY

1) INTRODUCTION

The moment I printed out the EUCLID Student Orientation document and the ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack I realized my Doctor of Philosophy (Ph.D.) journey had started. I have been longing to embark on the Ph.D. adventure since I completed my Master program. However, my finances were tight; therefore, I decided to begin to work and postpone my doctoral studies to a later time. As a relatively seasoned international professional, I have been working with the assumption that I would need to take a break from my career in order to be able pursue my Ph.D. dream. Discovering EUCLID's academic offer was a pleasant and relieving surprise, since its remote and part-time nature is compatible with the pursuit of my profession. For this reason, I was excited to get started with the ACA-401D course materials and I promptly began my studies.

My initial impression was that the quality of the learning offered by EUCLID is higher than my expectation. I found the reading material for the first course to be very accurate and comprehensive. Nevertheless, the contents of the ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack are also quite challenging for students who are unfamiliar with the basics of editing and have not been engaged in academic paper writing for a long time. I found it difficult to memorize the details of the concepts presented in the study material and I

realized that I may only be able to proficiently apply them through a lot of practice. Therefore, I am certain that this first Response Paper will serve as the perfect testing ground and it will help me to identify my major gaps in scholarly writing.

The key concepts that captured my attention during the study of the course materials included punctuation, plagiarism, citation and the use of a style guide. This Response Paper focuses on how I interacted with these four concepts and my understanding of their application in academic essay writing.

2) PUNCTUATION

After a first chapter dedicated to the basics of essay writing, the ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack deep dives into the usage of punctuation marks. The chapter starts with a general rule that I found to be very useful: “Use as little punctuation as necessary while retaining the meaning of the sentence” (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 16). This is particularly insightful guidance and a valuable reminder for non-native English writers. Differently, in my mother tongue punctuation plays an important role within sentence structure; the Italian language tends to privilege long sentences with vast usage of punctuation marks.

The chapter provides a detailed overview of the correct and incorrect ways to apply several commonly used punctuation marks, such as commas, colon, semicolon, brackets (round, square, angle and curly), dashes and hyphens, apostrophe and bullet points. On the latter, which I regularly use in work-related documents that I develop, I found it useful to review the punctuation rules at the end of bullet points. For instance I learnt that punctuation only applies at the end of the bullet point that contains a stand-alone sentence, manifesting in the form of a semicolon (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 18).

Overall I found the chapter to be difficult to read at once; I had to address one section at the time to try and memorize the different punctuation rules. I believe the contents of this chapter are better remembered when applied to essay writing. Therefore I have been looking forward to start working on my first Response Paper, using the Coursepack as a reference to practice the correct use of the punctuation marks discussed.

While not belonging to the dedicated punctuation chapter, I was particularly interested in the reference to punctuation differences between the American and British English. The last two sections of chapter three of the ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack focus on variations in the use of periods, commas and quotation marks. The examples provided made me realize that I was indeed confused about the subtle difference in the use of punctuation between these two main variants of the English language. I recognized that I was regularly combining the two punctuation standards within the same text, thus not applying a United States (US) or United Kingdom (UK) convention of grammar coherently.

3) **PLAGIARISM**

Chapter four of the ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack focuses on plagiarism, that is “when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information.” (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 34)

I am very familiar with this concept and in my writings I am particularly mindful about anchoring findings and ideas to their rightful author. This concept was introduced to me during secondary education, when we started to engage in substantive research and the writing of academic essays. It was further reinforced during my University studies, where plagiarism was treated as a serious offence.

As Cleenewerck & Gulma point out “plagiarism is wrong and unethical” (34) and it can manifest in different forms. The way to avoid plagiarism is to ensure proper citation of the source of the information presented (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 34). This leads me into another key concept discussed in the ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack, which I found particularly useful: *Citation*.

4) **CITATION**

Citation is a “method used to indicate where a piece of information came from” (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 34). Citation is – or should be – a broadly utilized practice in both professional and academic writing. When approaching a research topic, one of the initial steps to be undertaken by the author is to explore existing material of relevance to the subject (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 8). In this regard it is important to be able to distinguish credible sources that can provide useful information.

As a prolific writer in my work function, I spent time to review the section on citation in detail. This helped me to better appreciate the correct ways to cite at different instances: in-text, short quotations, long quotations and paraphrasing (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 35-37).

Similarly, I found especially interesting the explanation about “How to cite” and “When NOT to cite” (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 34 & 37). For example, I now appreciate that I can replace the in-text parenthetical quotation (Turabian style citation) by using instead the name of the author and a signal phrase at the beginning of the sentence to introduce the quotation or paraphrased concept (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 38).

Cleenewerck & Gulma also provide useful indications of when citation may not be necessary (37). In short, citing the source may be omitted if the idea or fact presented can be considered “common knowledge”, for example if a piece of information is referenced profusely across various sources.

5) **STYLE GUIDE AND CHICAGO STYLE**

Keeping a consistent writing style can improve the way a written product is perceived. Several international organizations, as well as private firms, develop style guides to set forth the standards of how visual and written contents should be produced and presented. This is particularly important for branding purposes for example, but also to ensure that the end product conveys an image of professionalism.

Cleenewerk & Gulma define a style guide as “a means of documenting your approach as a writer to certain elements of writing style that need to be consistent.” (41) As the authors point out, while there may be some natural propensity for some writers to abide by certain standard writing styles, adopting a style guide enhances coherence and consistency in the written product (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 41).

Chapter six of the ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack includes a focus on the use of abbreviations in line with the Chicago Style. This section made me reflect upon editing and formatting notions that I tended not to prioritize in my writing. While some concepts were already part of my practice, the details provided in the Coursepack contributed to a better understanding of how to refine text formatting in line with a coherent style guide.

For example, I would generally be mindful of introducing acronyms when I use them in a text for the first time. However, I was not aware of the need to abide by a standard format for this; that is, according to the Chicago Style, putting the acronym into brackets. In my previous writings I have been using indistinctively a dash or brackets to separate the acronym from its spelt out formulation. Moving forward, I will strive to better reflect the Coursepack guidance into my professional and academic writing.

6) **CONCLUSION**

Being the ACA-401D the entry point to my new Ph.D. adventure, for the first time I can now appreciate the complexity and depth of knowledge expected from a high-quality Ph.D. candidate. When I received the study materials for ACA-401D Period 1 I thought I would start at a full speed with my first Response Paper. However, once I began to familiarize with the ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack I realized that as a non-English mother tongue with only basic knowledge of editing and formatting, I would greatly benefit from a thorough review of the contents of the module.

Several chapters and sections proved to be extremely useful, although challenging at times, in particular the explanations on punctuation, plagiarism, citation and the use of a style guide. I enjoyed learning about the use of punctuation marks, including the differences between British and American English and how to properly cite within the text.

Moving forward I look forward to learning more about rules of style and getting acquainted with tools like Zotero and Grammarly Premium that can boost the quality of my academic writing.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *How to Write a Response Paper*. Bangui: Euclid University.

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